

EXPEDITIONS OF N. A. ZARUDNY IN IRAN (PERSIA)

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Abstract: Many travelers collected bird specimens from Iran (Persia), either to support their identifications or in order to unravel subspecies taxonomy of the birds of Iran. This article is trying to note expeditions by the world-famous ornithologist Nikolai Alekseevich Zarudny during his travels in Iran which have already published in different books or reported papers. Zarudny conducted four prominent expeditions during 1896 until 1904 to Eastern, Central, and Western parts of Iran. These expeditions supported by the Russian Academy of Sciences, the Russian Geographic Society, and the St. Petersburg Zoological Museum. He collected, identified, and published rich materials on the fauna of this region, especially on the birds. Zarudny deposited lots of skin materials of bird fauna of Iran that constitute about 11% of ornithological collection in National University of Uzbekistan. Herewith, his expedition routes and main finding has been explained in details in the text and on the maps. Each expedition is supplied with annotations, giving the localities and time of year where the bird observations had been made. These data are also superimposed on a separate maps supplied with coordinates. This information potentially could be used to prepare a historical atlas of observed distribution birds in Iran.

Keywords: Iran (Persia), Zarudny, Historical atlas, Birds

First expedition Eastern Iran, 1896

Travel 23 Mar to 29 Jul. Expedition in Khorasan and the Sistan basin. Listing 155 localities.

Main route: Goudan (Russian border), EmamQoli (23–24 Mar), DaulatKhaneh and Zubaran (25 Mar), Quchan (25 Mar), Farkhan and Hajjiabad (26 Mar), Seydabad (27 Mar), Nowbahar and Chanaran (27 Mar), Qasemabad (28 Mar), Mashhad (28 Mar–1 Apr), Toroq (2 Apr), Sharifabad (3 Apr), Khakestar (4 Apr), EslamQalah (4 Apr), Asadabad (5 Apr), Kaskak (6–7 Apr), Torbat-e-Heydariyeh (8 Apr), Umi (9 Apr), Buriabad (10 Apr), Dughabad, Abdolabad, and Feyzabad (11 Apr), Miandehi (12 Apr), Nusi and surrounding Bejestan desert (13–16 Apr), Marandiz (16 Apr), Chopal (16–17 Apr), Bejestan (17 Apr), Zeinabad (18 Apr), Firdaus (19 Apr), Burut (19–20 Apr), Surun (20 Apr), Sarayan (21–23 Apr), Dostabad (23 Apr), Mohammedabad (24–25 Apr), Chahak (26 Apr [encountering *Podoces pleskeias* new for science after leaving the village on the way to Rabatkazy]), Kalat-e Haj Yusef (27–28 Apr), Birjand (28 Apr–2 May), Bagyran-Kuhmt. and nearby Rekut (3–6 May), Khusf (7 May), Fadesh (8 May), Hamur

(9–10 May), SarChah (11 May), Feyzabad (12 May), Basiran (13–14 May), Rumeh (15 May), Ku Buvak valley (17 May), Sumofat and ChaharFarsakh (18 May), Nih (= Nehbandan, 19–20 May), Khunik-e Bala (21 May), Aliabad (22 May), Bandan (23–25 May), Neyzar at W shore of Sistan lakes (25–26 May and 3 Jun), Afzalabad at E shore Sistan lakes (27 May and 3 Jun), Husseinabad and Nasirabad (near present-day Zabol, 28 May–2 Jun). Return voyage over Bandan (4–6 Jun), Aliabad (7 Jun), Nehbandan (8–9 Jun), Arviz, Neyzabad and Khunik-e Bala (10 Jun), Tarq and Shivar (11 Jun), Larak and Esmailabad (12 Jun), Sahlabad and Ebrahimi (13 Jun), Kaidasht and Dastgerd (14 Jun), Golander (14–15 Jun), Gurid (16 Jun), Chahkand (17–18 Jun), another Dastgerd (18 Jun), Bojd (19 Jun), Birjand (19–20 Jun), Kalateh-ye Hajji Javad (21 Jun), Piranj (22 Jun), Rubokht, Nuk and Saqi (22 Jun), Sedeh (23 Jun), Owj and Rum (24 Jun), Qayen (25 Jun), Khunik-e Bala (25–27 Jun), Garmab (29 Jun), Boniabad (30 Jun), Soltanabad (= Aliabad, 1 Jul), Zuzan (2 Jul), Bokhsani (3–5 Jul), Khvaf (= Rud, 5 Jul), Laj and Salami (6 Jul), another Sedeh (7 Jul), Fathabad (8 Jul), Jarf (10–11 Jul), ChaharTakab and neighbouring Kale-Minar Mts. (11–13 Jul), Qalandarabad and

Fariman (14 Jul), Hoseynabad (15 Jul), Sang Bast and BazHowz-e Pain (16 Jul), Toroq (17 Jul), Mashhad (17–19 Jul), Kjardy (21 Jul), Jank (22–23 Jul), Marish (23 Jul), HazarMadjed Mts. pass (25 Jul), Khakistar (26–27 Jul), and Kheyraabad (28 Jul, at border S of Kaakhka in Turkmenistan)].

Second expedition Eastern Iran, 1898

Travel 14 Mar to 15 Nov 1898. Expedition in Khorasan and Sistan-Baluchestan, reaching south to the Bampur area and east to the Sistan basin. Listing 195 localities.

Main route: Goudan (Turkmenistan border S of Geok-Tepe, 14 Mar 1898), DorBadam (15 Mar), EmamQoli (15 Mar), DaulatKhaneh and Quchan (16 Mar), Nowbahar and Qasemabad (19 Mar), Mashhad (20–25 Mar), Toroq (26 Mar), BazHowz-e Pain and Sang Bast (27 Mar), Hoseynabad (28 Mar), Fariman (29 Mar), Qalendarabad (30 Mar), Bardu (31 Mar–1 Apr), Karizun and Sebek-Bala (1 Apr), Khorramabad (2 Apr), Langar (3 Apr), villages in Jam R. valley (3–5 Apr), Koshkak (5 Apr), Kariz (6 Apr), HariRud R. between Kariz and (in Afghanistan) Kafir-Kala (= EslamQaleh, 34°39'N, 61°03'E), also visiting Tirpul, Ghurian, and Zindajan in Afghanistan (7–10 Apr), back to Iran at Tayyebad and Farmanabad (11 Apr), Karat (12–14 Apr), HariShotur R. gorge (15 Apr), Sangan (15 Apr), Niazabad (16 Apr), Mozhnabad (17 Apr), Fandokht (18 & 22 Apr), Bazaa valley (19–21 Apr) towards Hauz-i-Muzaffariwatertank (20 Apr), Mirabad, Awis, and Now Deh (22 Apr), Mohammedabad (23 Apr), Ahangaran (24–25 Apr), Shahrakht (25 Apr), Gulmirun (26 Apr), Gazik (27 Apr), Avaz (28 Apr), Tabas (29 Apr), Rازه (30 Apr), Makhunik (1 May), Duruh (2 May), Chah-e Zirun well (4 May), Khvajeh-dow-Chagi well (5 May), Chah-e Guishe well (6 May), and Bandan (8 May), leaving Khorasan 9 May. Sistan depression entered at Vareng bay (W Sistan lakes, 10 May), Afzalabad (E shore Sistan lakes, 11 May), Zabol (12 May), Helmand R. and neighboring meadows and desert (13 May– 1 Jun, including visits to Afzalabad, Neyzar valley, and Varmal), Hoseynabad (3–4 Jun), Varmal (5 Jun), Hauzdar (7 Jun), Shila (9 Jun), leaving Sistan depression and entering Baluchestan

hills, where travelling SSW: Hormak (10–11 Jun), Chah-e Divan well (12 Jun), Mian Bazar (13 Jun), Zahedan (14–15 Jun), Gal-e-Chah well (19 Jun), Dak-i-Doh well (20 Jun), Korin (20–21 Jun), Shandak (22 Jun), Zaitok and Chah-e Ahmad (23 Jun), Podagi (24 Jun), and Shur-Ab (27 Jun), reaching Bampur depression near Bazman (29 Jun–3 Jul), visiting Kaskin (6 Jul), Bampur (8–12 & 27–29 Jul), upper and middle Bampur R. (15–26 Jul, including Ge = Nikshahr), Chashmeh-e Kaskin (31 Jul), Bazman (2–8 Aug). Bampur depression left at Galgir pass (9 Aug), travelling E over Pansareh (10 Aug), Talab (11 Aug), Shurabad (11–12 Aug), Podagi (14–15 Aug), Hamun-e Jaori reed marsh (15 Aug), Khun-Kaka (17 Aug), Deh-e Pabid (18 Aug) to the Kuh-e TaftanMts, of which foothills reached 20 Aug. Camp at Tamin (24 and 26–27 Aug), from where peak of

Kuh-e Taftanmt. reached (25–26 Aug), then back home over Ladiz (28 Aug), Dar Gibian (30 Aug), Bog (30 Aug), Bid

(31 Aug), Zahedan (1–2 Sep), Mian-Bazar (3 Sep), Kuh-e Malik Siahmt. (where borders of Iran, Pakistan and Afghanistan meet, 4 Sep), Chah-e Divan well (5 Sep), Hormak (5 Sep), Shila (6 Sep), Hauzdar (9 Sep), Varmal (10 Sep), deserts of SE Sistan depression (11–23 Sep), Vareng Bay (24–25 Sep, leaving Sistan 26 Sep), Bandan (27 Sep), Chah-e Gyushe well (29 Sep), Khvajeh-dow-Chagi well (30 Sep), Chah-iZirun well (1 Oct), Chah-i-Bani well (3 Oct), Hoseynabad and Ratuk (4 Oct), Dastgerd (5–6 Oct), Tabas (7 Oct), Gazik (8 Oct), Gulmirun (10 Oct), Ahangaran (11 Oct), Mohammedabad (12 Oct), Bamrud (13 Oct), Mozhnabad (15 Oct), Sangan (17 Oct), Tiz-Ab (18 Oct), Karat (19 Oct), Mashhad Rizeh (20–21 Oct), Pul-e Band (22 Oct), Mardanabad (23 Oct), Torbat-e Jam (24 Oct), Hajiabad (25 Oct), Kariz Now (27 Oct), Qalendarabad (28 Oct), Fariman (28 Oct), Hoseynabad and Sa'adabad (29 Oct), BazHowz-e Pain (30 Oct), Mashhad (31 Oct–9 Nov), Quchan (12 Nov), EmamQoli (13 Nov), DorBadam (14 Nov), and Russian border at Goudan (15 Nov 1898)].

Third expedition Eastern Iran, 1900–1901

Travel 5 Oct 1900 to 18 Aug 1901. Expedition

of the Russian Imperial Society for Geography under direction of N. Zarudny in eastern Iran from N Khorasan to S Baluchestan. Listing 213 localities.

Main route: Goudan (Turkmenistan border), Bajgiran (5 Oct), DorBadam and EmamQoli (6 Oct), DaulatKhaneh and Quchan (7 Oct), Seydabad and Nowbahar (9 Oct), Mashhad (10–18 Oct), Toroq (19 Oct), BazHowz-e Pain (20 Oct), Hoseynabad and Fariman (22 Oct), Qalendarabad (23 Oct), ChaharTakab (25–25 Oct), Niz-Ab (27 Oct), another Seydabad (28 Oct), Pul-e Band (31 Oct), Kariz (1 Nov), PeshRobot (2 Nov), HariRud valley (2–3 Nov), Farmanabad (4 Nov), Karat (5 Nov), Tiz-Ab (6 Nov), Sangan (7 Nov), Mozhnabad (8–9 Nov), Bamrud (12 Nov), Mohammedabad (13 Nov), Dezg-e Bala (14 Nov), Gulmirun (15 Nov), Gazik (16 Nov), Tabas (17 Nov), Dastgerd (18 Nov), Rud-i-Shur valley (19 Nov), Ratuk (20 Nov), Hoseynabad (21 Nov), Chah-i-Bani well (22 Nov), Chah-e Zirun well (24 Nov), Khvajeh-dow-Chagi and Chah-i-Guishe wells (25 Nov), and Bandan (26–27 Nov). This relatively rapid southward voyage through areas explored more thoroughly in previous years was followed by a long stay in the Sistan depression during 29 Nov–23 Dec, visiting, e.g. Vareng bay, Afzalabad, Husseinabad, Zabol, Neyzar valley, and Helmand River. Departed over Hauzdar (27 Dec) and the deserts of the SE Sistan basin (28–31 Dec 1900, e.g. Ramrod ruins) to reach the Baluchestan hills at Hormak (2–3 Jan 1901). Then to Zahedan (6–7 Jan) and along the Pakistan border over Bid (9 Jan), Dar Gibian (10 Jan), Ladiz (12–13 Jan), Mirkuh (14–15 Jan), Rig-e Malik (= Shahrak-e Tahlab, 18–19 Jan), Tahlab (21 Jan), Gurani (25 Jan), Naranu (27 Jan), and Mirkala (29–30 Jan) to Maksotag (3 Feb), turning south and west over Shastun (5–7 Feb) and Dehak (9 Feb) to Zaboli (11 Feb). The party then proceeded due south over Kuh-e Birg Mt. (12 Feb), Rud-i-Tud (14 Feb), upper Rud-i-Sarbaz R. (15–18 Feb), Sarbaz (19–20 Feb), Pirdan (21 Feb), MazanZamin (22 Feb), Pur (23 Feb), Rask (24 Feb), Kale Posht (25 Feb), Kaptegin-dukan (26 Feb), BahuKelat (1–2 Mar), Bal (4 Mar), Mir-Bazar (5 Mar), Kambil (8 Mar), Lekubal (9 Mar), and Tiskupan (10 Mar), reaching the Indian Ocean at ChahBahar (11–14

Mar) and Tis (15–16 Mar), visiting the sea-shore nearby. Back north over Park (17 Mar), Muman (18 Mar), Geh (= Nikshahr, 24–26 Mar), Kush (28 Mar), Nokhoch (30 Mar), Chanf (3–5 Apr), Shishapust (8 Apr), and GowharPosht (11 Apr) to Bampur and surroundings (13–17 Apr), then over Damin (21 Apr), Karevandar (25 Apr), Podagi (26 Apr), Gunich (27 Apr), Sadk (30 Apr–1 May), Nukabad (1 May), Tamandan (4–5 May), ChahZaman (7 May), Kulkuh (8 May), Lahremba (10 May), Sian Jangal (11 May), Tamin (12 and 14 May), Kuh-e Taftan Mt. (13 May), Ladiz (15 May), Dar Gibian (16 May), Bid (17 May), Zahedan (18 May), and Mian Bazar (19 May) to Hormak (20 May). Another visit made to the Sistan depression, reached over Kundar and Hauzdar (23 May), with much attention spend to the lakes, deserts, and more remote wells in the northern part (25 May–27 Jun, attending, e.g. Adimi, Afzalabad, Deh-e Dust, Deh-e Gazmeh, Deh-e Khammar [= Deh-e Deraz], Deh-e Malek Mohammed-e Oshtorak, Deh-e Najaf, Helmand River, Hoseynabad, Neyzar valley, Vareng bay, and Zabol). On leaving Sistan, travelled 27–28 Jun at night to avoid summer heat, reaching Bandan 28 Jun. Then home over Zeynelabad (29–30 Jun), Chah-i-Guishe well (30 Jun–1 Jul), Khvajeh-dow-Chagi well (1–2 Jul), Chah-e Zirun well (2–3 Jul), Chah-i-Bani well (5 Jul), Hoseynabad (6 Jul), Ratuk (7–8 Jul), Dastgerd (9–10 Jul), Tabas (11 Jul), Gazik (12–13 Jul), Gulmirun (15 Jul), Dezg-e Bala (16 Jul), Rud-e Ahangaran (17 Jul), Bamrud (20–21 Jul), Awis (22 Jul), Mozhnabad (24 Jul), Sangan (26 Jul), Tiz-Ab (27 Jul), Karat (28–29 Jul), Mashhad Rizeh (30 Jul), Pul-e Band (31 Jul), Torbet-e Jam (2 Aug), Langar (3 Aug), Kariz Now (4–5 Aug), Qalendarabad and ChaharTakab (6 Aug), Fariman (7 Aug), BazHowz-e Pain (9 Aug), Mashhad (10–13 Aug), Chanaran and Seydabad (15 Aug), Quchan (16 Aug), DaulatKhaneh and EmamQoli (17 Aug), and Goudan (at the Turkmenistan border, 19 Aug)]

Fourth expedition

Central and Western Iran, 1903–1904

Travel 16 Sep 1903 to 25 May 1904. An expedition of N. Zarudny, G. Gadd, and the taxidermist S.A. Aleksandrov, travelling from the SE Caspian Sea across Iran to the head of

the Persian Gulf and from there north to the SW Caspian Sea. Listing 137 localities.

Main route: Gumish Tepe (near Atrak R. mouth, 16 Sep), Bandar-e Gaz (16–18 and 22–24 Sep), Ashur-Ade island (19 Sep), Mian Kalehsand spit (20–21 Sep), Gorgan Bay (22–24 Sep), Gorgan (26 Sep–4 Oct), Garmabdasht valley (7–10 Oct), south across the Elburz Mts. between Tash (11–14 Oct) and Deh-e Molla (17 Oct), travelling SW over Damgan (19–26 Oct), Farat (27–29 Oct), Ma'abed (30 Oct), and Guleki (31 Oct) to Rashm (1 Nov), then south across the Dasht-e Kavir desert from Hussein-nan (2 Nov) to Howz Ser-i-Howz (5 Nov) and further over Jandaq (6–8 Nov), Howz-e Panj (9 Nov), Howz Ibrahim Jafar (12 Nov), Anarak (14–15 Nov), Robat-i-Fars (17 Nov), Na'in (18 Nov), Gardaneh-ye Balabad (19 Nov), Tudeshk (20 Nov), Kuhpayeh (21 Nov), Sajzi (22 Nov), and Gulnabad (23 Nov) to Jolfa and Esfahan (24 Nov–13 Dec). The party then crossed the Zagros Mts. over Felavarjan (14 Dec), Bistjan (15 Dec), Kharaji (17 Dec), Naghan (18 Dec), Dow Polan (19 Dec), Sarkhun (20–21 Dec), Shahil-ye Bala (22 Dec), and Dehdez (23–25 Dec), reaching lower country at the Malamir basin (Izeh, 27–28 Dec) and on the plains of Khuzestan: Qaleh-ye Tol (29 Dec), AlaKhvorshid (30 Dec), Chashmeh Rughani (31 Dec 1903–1 Jan 1904), Salmiyeh (3 Jan), Veys (4–5 Jan), Naseri and nearby Jabal Tnue Mt. (6–17 Jan), Kut-e Abdollah (18 Jan), Kut-e 'Omeyr (19 Jan), Mozaffari (20 Jan), Farsiat (21–22 Jan), Seba near Rahmaniye (24 Jan), Kharman (26 Jan), Khorramshahr (29–30 Jan and 2–5 Feb), reaching the Karun R. mouth on 2 Feb. On the way back, a longer period was spent in Ahvaz, Naseri, Jabal Tnue and surroundings (15–29 Feb), and the party then proceeded north over Band Qir (1 Mar), Shalili-yeh (2–4 Mar), Shushtar (5–6 and 21–22 Mar), Siah Mansur (8 Mar), Dezful (9–19 Mar), Kohnak (20 Mar), Perchestan (23 Mar), Pa Gach (25 Mar), Gulzar (26 Mar), Bid Zard (27 Mar), AlaKhvorshid (30 Mar), Qaleh-ye Tol (31 Mar), and the Malamir/Izeh basin (1–2 Apr). The Zagros was crossed again, from Dehdez (5–6 Apr) over Shahil-ye Bala (7 Apr), Sarkhun (8–9 Apr), Gamdalkal (10 Apr), Dow Polan (11 Apr), Naghan (12 Apr), Kharaji (13 Apr), and Bistjan (15 Apr) to Esfahan (17–21 Apr), but the expedition then travelled

north in the direction of the SW corner of the Caspian Sea instead of following a route to the NE parallel to the first part of the voyage: Gaz (22 Apr), Madar Shah (23 Apr), Murcheh Khvort (24 Apr), Gabr Abad (27 Apr), Kashan (28 Apr), Nasrabad (29 Apr), Pa Sangan (1 May), Qom (2–3 May), Reza'abad (5 May), Khoshkrud (7 May), Bu'in (9 May), Qazvin (11 May), Arisht (12 May), Aga Baba (13 May), Mulla Ali (14–15 May), Pa Chinar (16 May), Manjil (17 May), Rostamabad (18–19 May), Kara Rud R. (20 May), Lat (21–22 May), Rasht (23–24 May), Pir Bazar (24 May), ending in the harbour of Bandar-e Anzali (25 May 1904)].